

C stocks in abandoned Short Rotation Forestry (SRF) plantations in Central Italy

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Abstract

At the end of the last century, European Union (EU) energy policies encouraged the use of dedicated (Short Rotation Forestry or SRF) plantations in member countries in which fast-growing woody species are grown for energy purposes. Recently, in Italy some SRF plantations developed in the 90s have been abandoned or managed more extensively for economic and environmental reasons. However, these abandoned plantations can play a key role in biodiversity conservation and carbon storage. The present study is aimed to estimate carbon stock (C-stock) in living biomass and deadwood in three abandoned SRF plantations in Central Italy. The C-stock was estimated in three different 20-years SRF plantations (hybrid poplar, willow, black locust) located on the same site and unmanaged for 15 years. The results show a C-stock considering three of five C pools equal to: 47.30 MgC ha⁻¹ for hybrid poplar (65.3% in biomass and 34.7% in deadwood respectively), 23.02 MgC ha⁻¹ for willow (77.6% and 22.4% respectively), and 80.41 MgC ha⁻¹ for black locust (95.9% and 4.1% respectively). Outcomes of this research offer support for the forest restoration practices of similar abandoned SRF plantations. The application of extensive management techniques and the development of the naturalization process will ensure the role of biodiversity reservoir of these plantations, helping their evolution toward semi-natural systems mainly oriented to biodiversity conservation and climate change mitigation.

Introduction

At the end of the last century, Short Rotation Forestry (SRF) plantations – also known as short rotation woody crops (SRWC) or short rotation plantations (SRP) (Hoffmann and Weih 2005) – established for energy purposes rapidly expanded in European Union (EU) member countries with the aim to reduce fossil fuel dependence, greenhouse gases (GHGs) emissions, and waste production (Verwijst and Telenius 1999; Huber et al. 2018). SRF plantations have been

31 promoted, since the mid-80s, by the EU to improve land management, use the surplus agricultural land, increase the
32 production of wood raw material for industrial and energy uses (Bergez et al. 1991; Butler Manning 2015; Hall 1997).
33 In 1997, the EU White Paper on the strategy and action plan for renewable energy sources encouraged a substantial
34 increase of the SRF plantations area to fill the gap between wood supply and demand by both the renewable energy sector
35 and the traditional timber and wood processing industries (Dielen et al. 1997; Kuiper et al. 1998). Afterward, both the
36 Biomass Action Plan (EC 2005) and the Energy Policy for Europe (EC 2007) by the European Commission promoted the
37 use of energy from renewable sources such as solid woody biomass from forests and SRF plantations (Mola-Yudego and
38 Pelkonen 2008).

39 From a theoretical-conceptual point of view, SRF plantations can be defined as dedicated plantations in which woody
40 species are grown for energy purposes (González-García et al. 2012). In other words, SRF is a practice of cultivating fast-
41 growing trees that reach their economically optimum size in few years (e.g., usually from 1 to 15 years, but in any case
42 less than 30 years), employing intensive cultural techniques such as fertilization, irrigation and weed control, and utilizing
43 genetically superior planting material, relying on coppice regeneration, pests and diseases treatments (Ciccarese et al.
44 2014). Normally, density in SRF plantations is between 1,000-1,800 trees per hectare in the 5-year SRF plantations and
45 10,000-14,000 trees per hectare in the annual SRF plantations with a single-row or twin-row layout (Rosso et al. 2013;
46 Becenetti et al. 2016).

47 For all the above-described reasons, SRF plantations can be considered simplified ecological systems characterized by
48 low level of diversity compared to other plantations and to natural and semi-natural forests. The consequence of the low
49 ecological complexity is that their capacity to provide some ecosystem services, such as soil erosion protection (regulating
50 services) or habitat provision (supporting services), is reduced with respect to the above-mentioned forest systems
51 (Brockerhoff et al. 2013; Spence et al. 1999).

52 However, the biomass produced from SRF plantations trees – e.g., willow, black locust, and poplar – is used to provide
53 multiple goods and services such as fuel for electricity generation plants and soil amendment for clay caps (Nixon et al.
54 2021). In addition, SRF plantations may have a positive role as carbon (C) sink for atmospheric CO₂ (regulating services)
55 and biodiversity conservation (supporting services) based on their structure and location with respect to other land uses
56 like permanent crops or intensive agricultural areas (Smith and Watson 2011). The role of SRF plantations as a reservoir
57 of carbon and biodiversity in agricultural contexts is strictly related to more or less intensive cultural techniques applied
58 (e.g., short or medium cutting time, fertilization, weed control), structural complexity (horizontal and vertical structure)
59 of plantation, and amount of deadwood by component (i.e. lying deadwood, standing dead trees, stumps) and decay class
60 (Hardcastle 2006). In other words, biodiversity conservation and climate change mitigation are closely related to the type
61 of management adopted in the plantations which can be distinguished in (Paletto et al. 2014; Rubilar et al. 2018): (i)

62 intensive management for primary wood production; (ii) extensive management for wood production in an
63 environmentally sustainable way; (iii) no management or abandonment.

64 In Italy, approximately 10,000 ha of SRF plantations have been established from the end of the last century to the first
65 decade of the 2000s. The diffusion of SRF plantations in Italy is the result of European Union (UE) policies (EU Rural
66 Development, CAP reform) that encouraged the afforestation of agricultural land and improvement of woodlands through
67 subsidies (Tassone et al. 2004). Firstly, the Regulation (EEC) 2080/92 of June 30 1992 has had a significant impact on
68 the establishment of new plantations. After that the Rural Development Regulation (Council Regulation (EC) N°
69 1257/1999) has encouraged afforestation and agri-environmental interventions through the accompanying measures to
70 the 1992 reform. These plantations are mainly located in northern regions (Lombardy and Veneto) using fast-growing
71 species such as clones of poplar and willow, black locust, and plane tree (Becenetti et al. 2016). Recently, the importance
72 of SRF plantations has begun to decline due to the threat from damage by exotic pests or diseases (Hardcastle 2006; Koch
73 et al. 2011; Leslie et al. 2020) and to the economic-environmental performance worse than expected from these systems
74 (Pari and Suardi 2011; Becenetti et al. 2016). For these reasons, in many Italian regions SRF plantations established in
75 the last years are more sustainable systems managed with extensively approach through the reduction in tree density and
76 longer rotation periods. In this way, SRF plantations shift toward complex ecological systems characterized by higher
77 level of multifunctionality and ecological complexity (Di Candilo and Facciotto 2011).

78 Starting from these considerations, the aim of this study is to estimate the carbon stock (C-stock) in live biomass and
79 deadwood in abandoned SRF plantations. For this purpose, three SRF plantations established employing different tree
80 species and left to natural evolution after abandonment were considered in the present study. The research hypotheses is
81 that SRF plantations after abandonment can become an important C reservoir due to an accumulation of living and
82 deadwood biomass.

83

84 **Materials and methods**

85 *Site characterization and agronomic details*

86 The experimental site is the “Cà Rossi” farm (Fig. 1) located in Anzola dell’Emilia (Bologna province), in the alluvial
87 plain of Po Valley, Northern Italy (44°32’N, 11°11’E; 38 m a.s.l.). The soil of the site is a silt loam, classified as
88 Udifluventic Haplustepts fine silty, mixed mesic (Soil Survey Staff 2014). The main soil characteristics are reported in
89 Table 1. The local climate, classified as Cfa (C: warm temperate climate; f: fully humid – precipitation -; a: hot summer
90 – temperature) according to the Köppen climate classification (Kottek et al. 2006), is characterized by an annual average
91 precipitation of about 755 mm (thirty-years average annual total precipitation).

92 As shown in Annex 1, a field experiment on SRF plantations with a harvesting cycle of two years was established in
 93 March 2002, with the aim of comparing the bioenergy production of the following woody species (Di Candilo et al. 2008):
 94 i) hybrid poplar (*Populus x canadensis*); ii) willow (*Salix alba* L.) and ii) black locust (*Robinia pseudoacacia* L.). The
 95 three woody species – one native (white willow) and two non-native (hybrid poplar and black locust) – were established
 96 on three adjacent fields of 3500 m² each previously cultivated as arable land. The preceding crop was winter wheat. After
 97 the wheat harvest, the soil was ploughed at 0.30 m depth during the summer and subsequently refined with a rotary harrow
 98 during the winter to prepare favourable soil bed conditions for woody crops establishment.

99 Each field was composed by 12 rows of 162 m length, with a plant distance of 0.65 m along the rows and 1.8 m between
 100 the rows, resulting in a density of 0.85 plants per square meter. After transplantation, both hybrid poplar and willow were
 101 fertilized with 120 kg N ha⁻¹ in the form of urea and 52 kg P ha⁻¹ in the form of superphosphate; black locust, being a
 102 nitrogen-fixing legume, have received 52 kg P ha⁻¹ in the form of superphosphate, but not the N supply. Aiming at
 103 facilitating crop survival, in the transplant year three irrigations of 40 mm were applied in summer 2002 by sprinkler
 104 irrigation. In the following years, the crop stands were rainfed. Weeds were controlled mechanically during the first
 105 growing season.

106 Based on the harvesting cycle of two years, the three SRF stands were harvested in December 2003, 2005, and 2007. At
 107 harvest time, all aboveground biomass was removed at the height of about 0.1 m, by using farm-scale machinery. In the
 108 spring following the first and the second harvest, the fertilization schedule was repeated.

109 After the third cutting cycle, in 2007, the three plantations were abandoned and remained totally unmanaged up to the
 110 sampling time in July 2022. As a result, no agronomic input was applied, and no biomass harvest was managed.

111

112 **Table 1** Main chemical and physical characteristics of the soil for the upper layer 0.-0.2 m (g kg⁻¹)
 113

Chemical and physical characteristic	Mean ^a	SD ^{ab}
Sand (2.0-0.05 mm)	367	34.5
Silt (0.05-0.002 mm)	400	28.3
Clay (<0.002 mm)	233	27.4
pH in water	7.86	0.15
CaCO ₃ active	6.23	0.85
CaCO ₃ total	14.9	1.31
Walkley and Black SOC	10.6	0.14
Kjeldahl N	0.85	0.04

114 ^a Data redrawn from (Ceotto et al. 2018)

115 ^b Standard deviation

116

Study Area - Ca' Rossi- Anzola dell'Emilia

117

118 **Fig. 1** Location of the study area (“Cà Rossi”) in the Italy, Emilia-Romagna region

119

120 *Sampling and field measurements*

121 *Sampling method*

122 The field survey was conducted in June-July 2022, and data on living trees and deadwood were collected in three sample
123 plots, one for each SRF type. Being the three SRF plantations characterized by the same surfaces (3500 m²), sample plots
124 of the same size were adopted. In particular, circular sample plots of 9 m radius (368 m³) were used to investigated 8.0%
125 of total plantation area. The central point of each sample plot was randomly generated using the Random points inside
126 polygons routine of QGIS 2.18.7 (QGIS Development Team 2017), establishing at least one sample plot in each SRF
127 type.

128

129 *Field measurements*

130 In each sample plot, the main stand dendrometric parameters for all living trees were recorded such as: species and
131 diameter at breast height (DBH) for all trees with a diameter greater than 2.5 cm; height of the twenty trees nearest to the
132 center of the sample plot; and canopy closure. A DBH threshold of 2.5 cm for living trees has been adopted to survey also
133 young trees resulting from natural regeneration. The canopy closure is the proportion of sky hemisphere obscured by

134 vegetation when viewed from a single point and, with the maximum expansion's degree of its angle of view, it is a
135 projection of a hemisphere onto a plane (Paletto and Tosi 2009). In this study, the canopy closure was measured in the
136 center of the circular plot (see Fig. 5) using a spherical densiometer (Korhonen et al. 2006). In each survey point, four
137 measures in the directions N-W, N-E, S-W, S-E were taken, while the average canopy closure of the SRF plantation was
138 estimated as mean value of the four measures.

139 In each sample plot, the three deadwood components were surveyed and measured: lying deadwood (or logs); standing
140 dead trees (or snag); and stumps. The three components were distinguished using the classification proposed by De Meo
141 et al. (2017) and Bayraktar et al. (2020): all dead trees inclined less than 45° from the vertical line were considered as
142 standing dead trees, whereas those inclined more than 45° were included in lying deadwood. Trees broken at a height of
143 less than 1.30 m were classified as stump, while above 1.30 m of height were classified as standing dead trees. Regarding
144 the deadwood size, all woody debris with a diameter greater than 2.5 cm were recorded.

145 All standing dead trees (whole or truncated) and stumps included in the sample plot were identified and measured. For
146 each standing dead tree and stump, the following data were collected: species, two perpendicular diameters; height of the
147 standing dead tree or stump (cm); decay class using a 3-class classification system. Conversely, lying deadwood in the
148 sampling plot was measured using the Line Intersect Sampling (LIS) method (Warren and Olsen 1964; Van Wagner
149 1968). According to the line-intersect approach all lying woody debris that intersect the transect are measured at the point
150 of intersection of the transect and the central axis of the log (Marshall et al. 2000). The assumption of this approach is
151 that the cross-sections of all logs are circular. The transect length (L) is the key variable affecting the precision of the
152 estimate because the probability of sampling a woody debris piece is proportional to its length (Bell et al. 1996; Böhl and
153 Brändli 2007). In the present study, two transects of 18 m (total length L equal to 36 m) were located within the sample
154 plot passing through the center of it: the first transect in the direction North-South (N-S), while the second transect in the
155 direction East-West (E-W), perpendicular to the first one (see Fig. 2). Key information was recorded for each item
156 intercepted by two transects such as: species, two perpendicular diameters measured in the intersection point of the
157 transect, and decay class using a 3-class classification system.

158

159

160 **Fig. 2** Sample plot used for data collection in SRF plantations

161

162 During the field measurements the assignment of decay class for each deadwood piece is an important point to provide
 163 reliable C-stock estimates. As emphasized by many authors, decay class affects deadwood-inhabiting fungi, bryophyte
 164 presence and diversity (Ódor and Standovár 2001; Hammond et al. 2004; Ulyshen and Hanul 2010) as-well-as the C
 165 released to the atmosphere (Rock et al. 2008; Onodera and Tokuda 2015). In the international literature many different
 166 decay class systems with different class definitions are used ranging from three decay class systems to systems constructed
 167 with eight classes (Baker and Chao 2011; Næsset 1999; Seedre et al. 2013).

168 The most common system to assess decay class of deadwood in forests is realized distinguishing among five decay classes
 169 considering some visible characteristics, as in the Italian National Forest Inventory. In this system classes are defined
 170 modifying those proposed by Næsset (1999), and considering some important operational aspects underlined by
 171 Humphrey et al. (2004) to base classification exclusively on visual assessment (Di Cosmo et al. 2013).

172 In Table 2 is shown the 3-class classification system (Lee et al 1997; Yan et al 2006) that we adopted, as we find it more
 173 suitable to be applied in the present study.

174

175

Table 2 Description of 3-decay class by deadwood component (adapted from Lee et al. 1997)

Decay class	1 st	2 nd	3 rd
Lying deadwood	Bark intact and attached, small branches present, wood	Bark detached or in fragments, small branches absent, wood	Bark and small branches absent, wood consistency

	consistency intact, and very small rotten area under bark	consistency reduced, small rotten area	compromised, large rotten area
Standing dead trees	Bark intact and attached, small branches present, wood consistency intact, very small rotten area under bark	Bark detached or in fragments, small branches absent, wood consistency reduced, small rotten area	Bark and small branches absent, wood consistency compromised, large rotten area
Stumps	Bark intact and attached, wood consistency intact, very small rotten area under bark	Bark detached or in fragments, wood consistency reduced, small rotten area	Bark an absent, wood consistency compromised, large rotten area

176

177 *Sample collection*

178 In each sample plot, deadwood samples (cylindrical core) were collected using a battery drill (20.4 V) with a modified
 179 bit in accordance with the procedure proposed by Paletto and Tosi (2010). The modified bit concurred to remove standard
 180 cylinders of wood with a volume comprised between 15.30 cm³ and 56.52 cm³. The diameter of cylinder was fixed (3
 181 cm), while the length was variable, and it was measured by a calliper with an accuracy of 1/10 mm. A total of 63 deadwood
 182 samples were collected and distributed as follows: seven samples for each tree species and decay class.

183 In addition, five wood samples by living tree species (15 samples in total) were collected with the Pressler increment
 184 borer to estimate the basal area increment of living trees. In each sample plot, the five trees closest to the center of the
 185 plot were selected as sample trees.

186

187 *Laboratory analysis*

188 *Living tree samples*

189 The wood samples collected on living trees were analysed in the dendrochronology laboratory to estimate the growth
 190 trend for each species and current annual increment. For each tree species, the tree-ring chronology between 2008 and
 191 2021 (14 years) was analysed. One core per tree was extracted using a 5-mm diameter increment borer at breast height
 192 on the cross-side of the trunk. The increment cores were mounted on wooden supports, air-dried, and then smoothed with
 193 the slide microtome WSL-Core-microtome (Gärtner and Nievergelt 2010). Finally, transverse micro-sections with 15–20
 194 µm thickness and 10–20 cm length were cut from the entire increment cores using the above-mentioned slide microtome.
 195 Subsequently, tree-ring widths (TRW) were measured from bark to pith with a 0.01-mm precision. Measures were realized
 196 using a computer-linked measuring table (LINTAB™ 6, Rinntech, Germany) under a stereo microscope (Leica S9i,
 197 magnification range: 6.1X – 55X) and a software package (Time Series Analysis and Presentation, TSAP, Frank Rinn,
 198 Heidelberg, Germany). For this aim, the glass slides with the micro-sections were placed under the stereo microscope on

199 a special support raised from the measuring table and were analysed in transmitted light by inserting optical fibres from
200 below (Mazza et al. 2020).

201

202 *Deadwood samples*

203 The deadwood samples collected in the field were analysed in laboratory to estimate gravimetric moisture content (%)
204 and biomass (kg m^{-3}) for each tree species distinguishing between the three decay classes. In order to not affect the quality
205 of the deadwood samples and to not compromise the moisture content, the laboratory analysis was conducted within 24
206 hours after the sample collection in the field. The laboratory analyses have been carried out in two days according to the
207 procedure proposed by Paletto and Tosi (2010): in the first day the fresh weight of deadwood samples was determined
208 using an analytical balance. Then, the samples were dried in the stove for 24 hours at the temperature of 105°C. During
209 the second day the samples were re-weighed for the determination of the dry weight after cooling in a dryer with silica
210 gel.

211

212 *Data processing*

213 *Living trees*

214 The data collected in the field on living trees was used to estimate the following variables per hectare for each SRF type:
215 mean stand density (SD , n° of trees ha^{-1}), mean basal area (G , $\text{m}^2 \text{ha}^{-1}$), mean basal area diameter (Dg , m), mean height
216 (Hm , m), and mean volume (V , $\text{m}^3 \text{ha}^{-1}$).

217 The heights and diameters of the twenty trees nearest to the center of the plot were used to analyse the height-diameter
218 relationship for the three different SRF plantations. Using the logarithmic equation for each plot, height was estimated
219 for all unmeasured stems, giving a mean stem and dominant height.

220 Living trees volume and basic density by species were used to estimate C-stock of aboveground and belowground biomass
221 (MgC ha^{-1}) for each species using the following formula (eq.1):

222

$$223 \quad C_{stock-biomass_i} = CF \cdot [(V_i \cdot BWD_i \cdot BEF_i) \cdot (1 + R_i)] \quad (\text{eq.1})$$

224

225 Where: CF is the carbon factor; V_i is the volume of living tree (growing stock) for the species i ; BWD_i is the basic wood
226 density for the species i (kg m^{-3}); BEF_i is the biomass expansion factor for the species i ; R_i is root/shoot ratio for the
227 species i .

228 A preliminary literature review was made to identify the most suitable values for all variables used as shown in Table 3.

229

230 **Table 3** Average values for all variables used to estimate C-stock by species

Variables/Species	Hybrid poplar	Willow	Black locust
Basic wood density (<i>BWD</i>)	377	380	644
Biomass expansion factor (<i>BEF</i>)	1.20	1.20	1.32
Root/shoot ratio (<i>R</i>)	0.25	0.26	0.26
Carbon factor (<i>CF</i>)	0.498	0.506	0.500

231 Source: our elaboration from Matthews (1993), Desrochers and Thomas (2003), Tüfekçioğlu and Güner (2008), Klačnja
 232 et al. (2013), Taeroc et al. (2015), Lukić et al. (2015), Tolunay (2019).

233

234 Finally, the data analysed in the dendrochronology laboratory were used to estimate the basal area increment (BAI) by
 235 species using the following equation (eq.2) (Assmann 1970; Tenzin et al. 2017):

236

$$237 \quad BAI_i = \left[\frac{\pi(2 \cdot DBH_i \cdot I_d + I_d^2)}{5} \right] \quad (\text{eq.2})$$

238

239 Where: BAI_i is the observed 5-year periodic mean annual $BAIs$ ($\text{cm}^2 \text{yr}^{-1}$) for the last 5 years, DBH_i is the DBH at the
 240 beginning of the considered growth period (year 2008) in cm and I_d is the 5-year diameter increment in cm.

241

242 *Deadwood*

243 The data collected on deadwood was processed to estimate total and average deadwood volume by species (hybrid poplar,
 244 willow, black locust), component (logs, snags, and stumps), and decay class. The total volume (V_l) of lying deadwood
 245 per hectare, was estimated using the algorithm by van Wagner (1968) (eq.3):

246

$$247 \quad V_l = \left(\frac{\pi^2}{8L} \sum_{i=1}^N d_i^2 \right) \quad (\text{eq.3})$$

248

249 Where V_l is the volume of lying deadwood ($\text{m}^3 \text{ha}^{-1}$); L is the total length of the two transects in meters (m), N is the
 250 number of logs in the sample plot; and d_i is the average diameter (mean of the two orthogonal diameters) at the i
 251 intersection point (cm).

252 Standing dead tree volume (V_s) per hectare was estimated using standing dead tree basal area (BA) and tree height (h),
 253 this last obtained from the hypsometric curve by using the standard biometric equation (Cannell 1984) (eq.4):

254

|

$$V_s = \left(\sum_{i=1}^N f \cdot BA_i \cdot h_i \right) \cdot \frac{10000}{S} \quad (\text{eq.4})$$

256

257 Where V_s is the volume of standing dead tree ($\text{m}^3 \text{ha}^{-1}$); BA_i is the standing dead tree basal area (m^2); f is stem form factor
 258 as relationship between real stem volume and cylinder volume; S is the area of sampling plots (m^2); N is the number of
 259 standing dead trees in the sample plot; and h_i is height obtained from the hypsometric curve (m). A stem form factor (f)
 260 of 0.5 was used because it is considered suitable for broadleaved species with 5–10% of branches (Lang et al. 2016).

261 Stumps volume (V_{st}) per hectare was estimated using maximum and minimum height of the stump and diameter of cutting
 262 or slating plan as shown in the following formula (eq.5):

263

$$V_{st} = \left[\frac{\pi}{4} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{H_i + h_i}{2} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{D_i + d_i}{2} \right)^2 \right] \cdot \frac{10000}{S} \quad (\text{eq.5})$$

265

266 Where V_{st} is the volume of stump ($\text{m}^3 \text{ha}^{-1}$); H_i and h_i are maximum and minimum height of the stump (m), D_i and d_i are
 267 maximum and minimum diameter of the stump i at cutting or slating plan (m), N is the number of stumps in the sample
 268 plot, while S is the area of sample plot (m^2).

269 The data obtained from the laboratory analyses were used to estimate: i) fresh or green density (fresh mass divided by
 270 fresh volume), ii) basic or dry density (oven-dry mass divided by fresh volume), iii) moisture content, defined as the
 271 weight of water in wood expressed as a fraction, usually a percentage (%), of the weight of oven-dry wood.

272 The results of the laboratory analyses allowed to determine fresh density (FDD), basic deadwood density (DDB), and
 273 moisture content (MC_d) of deadwood by tree species and decay classes.

274 Deadwood volume and basic density by component and decay class were used to estimate C-stock of the deadwood pool
 275 using the following formula (eq.6):

276

$$C_{stock-deadwood} = CF \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n [(Vl_i + Vs_i + Vst_i) \cdot DDB_i] \quad (\text{eq.6})$$

278

279 Where: CF is the carbon factor; Vl_i , Vs_i and Vst_i are respectively the volume of lying deadwood, standing dead trees, and
 280 stumps of decay class i ; DDB_i is the basic deadwood density of decay class i (kg m^{-3}); and n is the number of decay classes
 281 (3).

282

283 **Results**

284 **Living trees**

285 The main stand dendrometric variables – mean stem density (*SD*, stems ha⁻¹), basal area (*G*, m² ha⁻¹), mean basal area
286 diameter (*Dg*, cm), mean height (*Hm*, m), volume (*V*, m³ ha⁻¹), mean canopy closure (*CC*, %) – are shown in Table 4,
287 while the height-diameter relationship for the three types of SRF plantations in Annex 2.

288 The results show a stem density of 6,525 stems ha⁻¹ in the black locust plantation, with a basal area of 27.6 m² ha⁻¹. A
289 stem density of 1,257 stems ha⁻¹ were calculated in the willow SRF plantation with a basal area of 7.2 m² ha⁻¹, and in the
290 poplar SRF plantation 865 stems ha⁻¹ with a basal area of 14.1 m² ha⁻¹. The stem density values are also confirmed by the
291 canopy closure estimation with the spherical densiometer: from a minimum of 74.1% in hybrid poplar SRF plantation to
292 a maximum of 93.6% for black locust SRF plantation.

293 Observing the data of volume, the results highlight a range of values between a minimum of 36.26 m³ ha⁻¹ for willow SRF
294 plantation and a maximum of 144.61 m³ ha⁻¹ for black locust SRF.

295 Currently, after twenty years from the plantation (2002-2022) and fifteen years without active management (2008-2022),
296 hybrid poplar SRF plantation reached highest tree dimensions (*Dg* and *Hm*) due to its fast growth, while black locust SRF
297 plantation reached highest stand volume due to its high vegetative reproductive strength.

298

299 **Table 4** Main dendrometric variables for the three SRF plantations

Species	<i>SD</i> (n° ha ⁻¹)	<i>G</i> (m ² ha ⁻¹)	<i>Dg</i> (cm)	<i>Hm</i> (m)	<i>V</i> (m ³ ha ⁻¹)	<i>CC</i> (%)
Hybrid poplar	865	14.07	14.40	16.7	108.70	74.1
Willow	1,257	7.22	8.55	9.3	36.26	86.3
Black locust	6,525	27.55	7.33	10.9	144.61	93.6

300

301 The results about diameter distribution (Fig. 3) show that 84.4% of trees in willow SRF plantation are included in two
302 diameter classes: between 5-10 cm (43.8% of total trees) and 11-15 cm (40.6%). The black locust SRF plantation, shoes
303 88.9% of trees with diameter lower than 10 cm: 29.8% of total trees with diameter lower than 5 cm, while 59.1% between
304 5 and 10 cm. The hybrid poplar SRF plantation is characterized by a different situation, with 36.4% of total tree with
305 diameter between 5 and 10 cm and 31.8% between 16 and 20 cm. In addition, it is interesting to highlight that native
306 species – oak (*Quercus* spp.), maple (*Acer* spp.), elder (*Sambucus nigra* L.) – are establishing in hybrid poplar and willow
307 plantations. In hybrid poplar SRF plantation, native species represent 27.3% of number of trees and 7.0% of basal area
308 (0.98 m² ha⁻¹), while in willow SRF plantation represent 12.5% of number of trees and 7.1% of basal area (0.51 m³ ha⁻¹).

309 Conversely, in the black locust plantation there are no native species with a diameter greater than 2.5 cm.

310

311 **Fig. 3** Living tree diameter distribution by SRF plantations

312

313 *Diameter and basal area increment*

314 The dendrochronology analyses show a decreasing trend for all three species: in the period 2008-2014, an average
 315 diameter increment of 5.87 ± 2.33 cm for hybrid poplar, 1.01 ± 0.35 cm for willow, and 0.99 ± 0.41 cm for black locust,
 316 while the average diameter increments decreased to 0.65 ± 0.21 cm for hybrid poplar, 0.66 ± 0.21 cm for willow, and
 317 0.56 ± 0.15 cm for black locust in the period 2014-2015.

318 The mean BAI by species are equal to 10.93 cm yr⁻¹ for hybrid poplar, 4.44 cm yr⁻¹ for willow, and 6.15 cm yr⁻¹ for black
 319 locust.

320

321 *Deadwood*

322 The results show an average deadwood volume of 119.7 m³ ha⁻¹ (0.037 m³ per deadwood piece) in the hybrid poplar SRF
 323 plantation distributed among the three components as follows: 53.0% of deadwood volume in standing dead trees, 43.4%
 324 in lying deadwood, and the remaining 3.6% in stumps. Conversely, the other two SRF plantations are characterized by
 325 lower deadwood amounts: 31.7 m³ ha⁻¹ (0.012 m³ per deadwood piece) in the willow SRF plantation (84.4% in standing
 326 dead trees, 13.7% in lying deadwood, and 1.9% in stumps) and 16.7 m³ ha⁻¹ (0.011 m³ per deadwood piece) in the black
 327 locust SRF plantation (27.0% in standing dead trees, 70.5% in lying deadwood, and 2.5% in stumps).

328 Observing the deadwood amount by decay class, the results show higher volumes in the 2nd decay class for poplar SRF
 329 plantation (66.1 m³ ha⁻¹) and willow SRF plantation (14.5 m³ ha⁻¹), while for black locust SRF plantation the highest

330 volumes are in the 1st decay class (9.2 m³ ha⁻¹). Since plantations are 20 years old, the low amounts of deadwood in the
331 3rd decay class (10.65 m³ ha⁻¹ for hybrid poplar, 7.88 m³ ha⁻¹ for willow, and 1.86 m³ ha⁻¹ for black locust) are in line with
332 expectations.

333 Deadwood volume distribution by SRF type, decay class and component are shown in Table 5.

334

335 **Table 5** Distribution of mean deadwood volume (m³ ha⁻¹) in SRF plantations by component and decay class

SRF type	Component	Decay class 1	Decay class 2	Decay class 3
Hybrid poplar	Logs	0.00	42.93	8.98
	Snags	42.97	20.46	0.00
	Stumps	0.00	2.69	1.67
Willow	Logs	0.00	0.07	4.27
	Snags	9.29	14.01	3.40
	Stumps	0.00	0.40	0.21
Black locust	Logs	5.84	4.26	1.68
	Snags	3.34	1.16	0.01
	Stumps	0.00	0.25	0.17

336

337 The results about diameter distribution of deadwood (Fig. 4) show that in the hybrid poplar and willow plantations the
338 three deadwood components are characterized by a prevalence of elements in the diameter class between 5 and 10 cm
339 (65.1% and 63.8% of total deadwood elements respectively). Conversely, in the black locust plantations most deadwood
340 elements are in the diameter class lower than 5 cm (74.7%). In addition, it is important to emphasize that woody debris
341 with a diameter greater than 10 cm are only 32.5% of total deadwood elements in hybrid poplar, 10.1% in willow, and
342 3.3% in black locust SRF plantations.

343

344
345 **Fig. 4** Deadwood diameter distribution by SRF plantations

346
347 **Moisture content, fresh and dry density of deadwood**

348 The laboratory analyses on deadwood produced the data shown in Table 6 on moisture content (%), fresh and dry density
349 (g cm^{-3}) for the three species. The data evidence that the highest moisture values are recorded for the third decay class
350 both for willow (mean value of 19.8%) and black locust (26.0%) SRF plantations, while for hybrid poplar the highest
351 value is evidenced for the first decay class (40.1%). The non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test ($\alpha=0.05$) show statistical
352 significant differences of moisture content among decay classes for two of the three species: hybrid poplar ($p=0.007$) and
353 black locust ($p<0.0001$).

354 Regarding fresh and dry density, the results show a decreasing trend from the first to the third decay class, except the
355 second decay class of the black locust which records the highest values of both fresh (0.52 g cm^{-3}) and dry (0.46 g cm^{-3})
356 density. The non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test ($\alpha=0.01$) show no statistically significant difference for the three species
357 for both fresh and dry density.

358 The results about the water storage in lying deadwood highlight the following ranges of values by species: between 43.5
359 (3^{rd} decay class) and 112.6 (1^{st} decay class) kg m^{-3} for hybrid poplar; between 45.3 (2^{nd} decay class) and 61.9 (3^{rd} decay
360 class) kg m^{-3} for willow; and between 62.3 (2^{nd} decay class) and 94.1 (3^{rd} decay class) kg m^{-3} for black locust.

361
362 **Table 6** Moisture content (MC_d), fresh (FDD) and dry (BDD) density of deadwood by tree species and decay class
363 (Mean \pm SD)

Species	Moisture content (%)			Fresh density (g cm^{-3})			Dry density (g cm^{-3})		
	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3

Hybrid poplar	40.1±15.9	17.7±5.8	18.5±5.4	0.39±0.09	0.32±0.06	0.28±0.08	0.28±0.05	0.28±0.06	0.24±0.07
Willow	13.7±3.1	16.0±5.2	19.8±6.0	0.43±0.12	0.35±0.08	0.37±0.12	0.38±0.11	0.30±0.08	0.31±0.10
Black locust	18.1±3.0	13.4±0.7	26.0±8.6	0.42±0.20	0.52±0.12	0.43±0.29	0.36±0.17	0.46±0.11	0.34±0.21

364

365 ***C-stock in living biomass and deadwood***

366 The results illustrated in Table 7 about the estimation of living biomass C-stock show the following average values for
 367 the three SRF plantations: 30.9 MgC ha⁻¹ for hybrid poplar, 17.9 MgC ha⁻¹ for willow, and 77.2 MgC ha⁻¹ for black locust.

368 The higher C-stock values in black locust SRF plantation are due to both the higher average volumes and higher basic
 369 wood density of the black locust compared to the other two species: average volume of 144.61 m³ ha⁻¹ for black locust
 370 vs. 108.70 m³ ha⁻¹ and 36.26 m³ ha⁻¹ for poplar and willow respectively; basic wood density of 0.644 g cm⁻³ for black
 371 locust vs. 0.377 g cm⁻³ and 0.380 g cm⁻³ for poplar and willow respectively.

372 The results concerning deadwood C-stock evidence that the highest values are found for hybrid poplar SRF plantation
 373 (16.42 MgC ha⁻¹), while the lowest for black locust plantations (3.26 MgC ha⁻¹). Based on these results, the deadwood-
 374 living biomass C-stock ratio is within a range between 0.042 for black locust and 0.531 for hybrid poplar.

375

376 **Table 7** Average value of C-stock (MgC ha⁻¹) by tree species

	C-stock above-ground biomass	C-stock below-ground biomass	C-stock deadwood
Hybrid poplar	24.70	6.18	16.42
Willow	14.18	3.69	5.15
Black locust	61.23	15.92	3.26

377

378 **Discussion**

379 ***Renaturalization of SRF plantations***

380 The tendency of last years to realize more sustainable SRF plantations extensively managed, or the plantations abandoned
 381 for economic or ecological reasons can play an important role in the provision of ecosystem services. Concerning
 382 biodiversity conservation, these systems can act as a biodiversity reservoir with a crucial role for habitats connectivity
 383 (Kleinn and Morales 2001; Paletto and Chincarini 2012; Saura et al. 2014). The role of SRF plantations is especially
 384 important if these plantations are located in areas of intensive agriculture typical of many regions of northern Italy.
 385 However, more than 20 years are needed to start a renaturalization process and to reach an amount of deadwood sufficient
 386 to support saproxylic species (Hardcastle 2006; Smith and Watson 2011). In the present study, after 15 years of non-
 387 management a renaturalization process has been triggered, with the occurrence of native species which, in the future, will
 388 substitute the non-native ones (i.e. black locust and hybrid poplar).

389 In particular, in the willow plantation 12.5% of total trees (corresponding to 7.1% of total basal area) are native species,
390 while the remaining 87.5% are willow trees. In hybrid poplar plantation, the regeneration of native tree and shrub species
391 equal to 27.3% of total trees and 7.0% of basal area. Furthermore, the high amount of deadwood also confirms the
392 renaturalization process, and willow plantation is characterized by 31.7 m³ ha⁻¹ of deadwood and a deadwood-living
393 standing tree volume ratio equal to 0.87. Similarly, in hybrid poplar plantation deadwood volume is equal to 119.7 m³ ha⁻¹
394 ¹ corresponding to a deadwood-living standing tree volume ratio of 1.10. Conversely, black locust plantation is
395 characterized by low quantities of deadwood (16.7 m³ ha⁻¹) and the almost total absence of native species in the
396 regeneration layer, due to strong regeneration power of this species. It is important to highlight that deadwood in black
397 locust plantation is mainly composed of very fine woody debris presumably below the threshold considered in the present
398 study (diameter greater than 2.5 cm). Black locust still has the characteristics of a managed SRF plantation to produce
399 bioenergy, but with longer rotation periods (more than 15 years). Besides, the presence of deadwood in the different
400 components and decay classes has had a positive impact on the saproxylic species acting as a reserve of both C and
401 biodiversity. Deadwood variability by component and decay class positively influences both the release times of C into
402 the atmosphere and the microbial (fungi, bacteria, actinobacteria) and ciliate community diversity. At the same time, after
403 15 years of non-management, the high amount of deadwood and the native species (i.e. maple, oak, elder) establishing in
404 the regeneration layer demonstrate that a renaturalization process has been triggered.

405

406 ***Importance of deadwood in SRF plantations***

407 The 3rd Italian National Forest Inventory (NFI) estimated a living tree volume of 86.5 m³ ha⁻¹ for the hybrid poplar
408 plantations and 43.8 m³ ha⁻¹ for the other broadleaved plantations (Di Cosmo and Gasparini 2022), and a deadwood
409 volume of 5.0 m³ ha⁻¹ for the artificial plantations in general (Di Cosmo and Floris 2022). Therefore, the deadwood-living
410 trees volume ratio in the managed artificial plantations in Italy is included in a range between 0.06 and 0.11. Therefore,
411 our results about the deadwood-living trees volume ratio are closer to those of forests rather than artificial plantations (see
412 Lombardi et al. 2010 for a review of values in different forest types in Italy).

413 Another key aspect connected to the presence of deadwood in SRF plantations is related to the accumulation of water in
414 the dry season. According to Přívětivý and Šamonil (2021), deadwood – with special regard to downed deadwood – plays
415 a key role in increasing the water storage capacity of forest ecosystems and providing resources for organisms. A fortiori,
416 lying deadwood can play a fundamental role as a water reservoir for organisms in Mediterranean agricultural contexts as
417 our case study. The higher importance of lying deadwood compared to standing dead trees is due to the position of the
418 logs whether in contact with the ground or not. This parameter can influence the moisture content in relation to the amount
419 of contact area with the ground and, subsequently, the activity of decomposers and the composition of fungal communities

420 (Rajala et al. 2012; Přivětivý and Šamonil 2021). In the present study, the high lying deadwood volume ($51.9 \text{ m}^3 \text{ ha}^{-1}$ and
421 $11.8 \text{ m}^3 \text{ ha}^{-1}$ respectively) in the hybrid poplar SRF plantation and black locust SRF plantation has a key importance as a
422 water reservoir for microorganisms particularly in the Mediterranean areas (on average 76.0 kg, 51.4 kg and 66.5 kg of
423 water per m^3 of deadwood of the 1st, 2nd and 3rd decay class respectively). In particular, the role of lying deadwood as
424 water reservoir is of key importance in the less dense SRF plantations located in the Mediterranean area (e.g., hybrid
425 poplar SRF plantation in this study).

427 *The role of SRF plantations in climate change mitigation*

428 Regarding C-stock in SRF plantations, the results of the present research show in 20-years SRF plantations a C-stock
429 equal to: $47.30 \text{ MgC ha}^{-1}$ for hybrid poplar SRF plantation, $23.02 \text{ MgC ha}^{-1}$ for willow, and $80.41 \text{ MgC ha}^{-1}$ for black
430 locust. These values include aboveground biomass, belowground biomass, and deadwood, that means three of the five
431 carbon pools. The higher C-stock in black locust SRF plantation is due the highest annual volume increments recorded in
432 the period 2008-2021 and the lower number of dead trees compared to the other two species. Conversely, hybrid poplar
433 and willow SRF plantations are characterized by a high deadwood C-stock corresponding to 34.7% ($16.42 \text{ MgC ha}^{-1}$ on
434 $47.30 \text{ MgC ha}^{-1}$) and 22.4% (5.15 MgC ha^{-1} on $23.02 \text{ MgC ha}^{-1}$) of total C storage respectively, while this percentage is
435 equal to 4% (3.26 MgC ha^{-1} on $80.41 \text{ MgC ha}^{-1}$) in black locust plantation. Our results are in line with other studies about
436 C storage in SRF plantations. In a recent study conducted on a black locust SRF plantation in Lazio region (Central Italy),
437 Ciccarese et al. (2014) highlighted a C-stock at the end of the rotation period (15 years) equal to $39.21 \text{ MgC ha}^{-1}$ thus
438 distributed among C pools: 17.5 MgC ha^{-1} in above-ground biomass (44.6% of total), 5.47 MgC ha^{-1} in below-ground
439 biomass (14.0%), 3.2 MgC ha^{-1} in litter (8.2%), $12.05 \text{ MgC ha}^{-1}$ in soil (30.7%), and 0.99 MgC ha^{-1} in deadwood (2.5%).
440 In a study conducted in Serbia (Grdelica Gorge), Lukić et al. (2015) estimated in a 60-years old black locust plantation a
441 C-stock of 45.4 MgC ha^{-1} and 17.4 MgC ha^{-1} in living biomass and deadwood respectively. In three 7-years old SRF
442 plantations established with different poplar clones in northwest China, Meifang et al. (2017) estimated a living biomass
443 C-stock between $50.34 \text{ MgC ha}^{-1}$ for *Populus balsamifera* clone to $128.01 \text{ MgC ha}^{-1}$ for *Populus deltoides* clone.

444 Finally, it is important to point out that in abandoned natural and artificial systems, ecosystem services supply is sub-
445 optimal and forest restoration practices are the tool to regain ecosystem functionality and the forest capacity to provide
446 multiple ecosystem services (Marchi et al. 2018). As emphasized by Valasiuk et al. (2018), sustainable forest restoration
447 practices are finalized at regaining ecological functionality and delivering a wide range of ecosystem services. To
448 implement a sustainable forest restoration, it is fundamental to apply a transdisciplinary and multi-dimensional approach
449 through management treatments influencing one or more key variables related to stand structure such as tree species
450 composition, structural diversity, stand density. Management interventions must be oriented to realize a positive and

451 synergistic relationships between ecosystem services provided by these systems (Ruddell et al. 2007). The results of the
452 present study about the deadwood-living biomass C-stock ratio indicate that abandoned SRF plantations requires the
453 implementation of restoration practices in order to maintain stand vitality and the provision of ecosystem services.

454

455 **Conclusions**

456 The results provided by the present research can be considered a first step to understand the carbon cycle dynamics in
457 abandoned SRF plantations. It is important to specify that the data of the study refer to a limited area plantation (3500
458 m²) and to a specific context, and for this reason results must be considered preliminary. Based on the data obtained from
459 the survey, the three abandoned SRF plantations are characterized by a high C-stock but with a different distribution in
460 the three C pools that we have investigated. In hybrid poplar and willow SRF plantations, deadwood C pool plays a key
461 role in carbon storage by contributing between one-fifth and one-third of the C-stock, while in the black locust SRF
462 plantation carbon is stored almost exclusively in live biomass (more than 95% of C-stock). Besides, our results show that
463 the vitality of non-native species influences the renaturalization process. In fact, no native-species have been identified in
464 the black locust SRF plantation, while in the hybrid poplar and willow SRF plantations they are 27.3% and 12.5% of total
465 species respectively.

466 The present study can contribute to understanding and mapping the dynamics that are occurring in abandoned SRF
467 plantations and to improve the management in these areas which are widely replicable to similar contexts.

468

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470

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649 **Ethics Declarations**

650 **Conflict of interest**

651 The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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